

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING METACOGNITIVE STRATEGIES IN TEACHING SPEAKING

Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi

nafisateshaboyeva@gmail.com

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek

The Faculty of Psychology, the department of Foreign languages
Philology and teaching languages

Student of group 103-23: Po'latova Guli Nuriddin qizi

Abstract: this research aimed to find out the student ability in speaking at students t Junior High School 2 Panca Rijang and this study is the result of a report from a case study on the effect of metacognitive teaching on speaking ability of lowranking junior high school students, the metacognitive strategy influences students' speaking achievement, namely by conducting a pre-test in one group and the design of the post-test was conducted to support the findings in the results of learning speaking after training. In design, observation and qualitative questionnaires were conducted to see the process of students in learning speaking procedural knowledge of metacognition in speaking. This research applying metacognitive strategies that are developed as a way of learning. Subject, selected by simple random sampling, are 20 first grade junior high schools, Comparison of pre-test and post-test scores will show metacognitive strategy can help students who are less skilled improve their speaking skills. The results show the view that metacognitive strategy can help students with speaking skills who are less skilled improve their speaking skills, but from the overall results there still appear to be some limitations for those who are skilled with minimal results.

Keyword: metacognitive, speaking skill, junior high school, post-test scores, pre-test, vocabulary mastery test, daily vocabulary.

Introduction

Weak speaking ability, or difficulty understanding English because they are not used to speaking. External factors include English teachers who do not have the right

method of teaching speaking, facilities and infrastructure to learn speaking with low quality or classmates' interference. Various ways can be done by English teachers to overcome these obstacles one of them by using metacognitive methods. used to help students understand the way they learn; in other words, it means processes designed for students to 'think' about their 'thinking'. In describing the learning strategy, there are many definitions of learning strategy described by experts. Oxford (1990: 1) describes learning strategies as 2 steps taken by the language students to enhance their learning in the form of direct and indirect strategies. The definition has created a remarkable impact in the realm of SLA. This explanation requires effort made by students that is to develop their way of learning. Oxford divides LLSs into two parts: direct and indirect strategies. Numerous studies have shown positive effects of metacognitive strategy training on language performance. Those studies are on the focus of language skills. There have, however, been relatively few studies investigating the benefits of providing second language students with metacognitive strategy training to promote speaking skill. The other kind of study about metacognitive strategy training shows its positive impact on metacognitive strategy awareness. They show improvement of strategy use after training conducted. However, there are no details of metacognitive strategy use in the process. Before moving on to metacognitive learning, it is important to explain the term metacognitive. Flavel (1976) in Cross (2010) mentions that metacognitive means that determines one's cognitive process. In other words, think about ways of thinking. Metacognitive learning has two aspects: intentional or conscious performance of cognitive functions and knowledge and beliefs about cognitive processes. Another purpose of this research is to socialize metacognitive learning that still sounds familiar to English teachers in schools and courses and adds to the knowledge of methods and techniques of metacognitive learning

Background of the study This study is concerned with investigating students' skill who have low ability, it is commonly known that speaking is an important skill in learning a language because Language is a tool for communication. We communicate with others, to express our ideas, and to know others' ideas as well. Communication takes place, where there is speech. Without speech we cannot communicate with one another, the use of language is an activity which takes place within the confines of our community. We use language in a variety of situations. People at their workplaces, i.e. researchers working either in a medical laboratory or in a language laboratory, are supposed to speak correctly and effectively in order to communicate well with one another. Further explanation describes metacognition can most usefully be thought of as knowledge, skills, strategies, and information about cognition. From function side,

cognition acts to resolve problems and bring cognitive activity to a desirable outcome, while the metacognitive function is the monitoring and regulation of an individual's cognitive effort in solving a problem and executing a task .

Metacognitive Strategies: Metacognitive strategies can positively impact students who have learning disabilities by helping them to develop an appropriate plan for learning information, which can be memorized and eventually routine. As students become aware of how they learn, they will use these processes to efficiently acquire new information, and consequently, become more of an independent thinker. As a consequence of applying metacognitive strategies, students demonstrate an important improvement in their participation in class. Stuever observes that students increase their motivation for learning and participating actively every day for ten days. The results were positive, determining that it is possible to incorporate metacognition in traditional classrooms providing with an encouraging way of learning b. English Language Methodology Likewise, Bromley determines that there is not a specific method for teaching students. She recommends the application and combination of various methods because students have different learning styles, that is why it is relevant to take into account diverse methods that enhance the learning process. Larsen-Freeman maintains that methods serve as a foil for reflection that can aid teachers and students in bringing to conscious awareness the thinking that underlies their actions. According to Larsen Freeman, the application of various methods has in common the views that first, language can best be learnt when it is taught through communication, and second, that language acquisition can be upgraded by working not only on language, but also on the process of learning c. English Speaking Harmer states that: “the ability to speak fluently presupposes not only knowledge of language features, but also the ability to process information and language “on the spot” (p. 269). He also claims that during the process of teaching speaking or producing this English ability would be essential to apply them in three important sections: new language, practice and communicative activity. The ability of speaking is important for career success. Speaking skills can enhance one's personal life, thereby bringing about the well rounded growth they should all seek. Nunan expresses that speaking is an essential and executable tool for communicating with others Learning Procedure Researchers carry out the procedure carried out by Cross (2010) in his research. The pedagogical cycle includes a bottom-up strategy, sharing, discussion, and evaluation of strategies. In the first stage, students read conversation in the text book. Students identify words they don't understand then discuss them together. This is to prepare students and facilitate them in using strategies such as inference or elaboration. Then, students

discuss the text and share their opinions on the topic. Then the students listened to recorded conversation for 1-2 minutes, Students then answer the pre-test questions given as many as ten questions. In answering questions they can discuss to help them gather information that they passed. Then they collect their pre-test which is directly processed by researchers. Then, the researcher teaches the pedagogical cycle and strategies for listening, the researcher gives a second text to prepare for listening and practicing the conversation. And the last students evaluate their performance and the strategies they use for other activities. Students work on post-test. Vocabulary Mastery Test is testing someone's knowledge in understanding and comprehending words meaning and can be used in arranging the sentence to communicate. The scope of vocabulary is not only in diction but also it must be suited with the situation and the person who become partner in the communication. In this case with low ability students, the test is arranged to be easier and using daily vocabulary that they usually use in their activities The procedure of these two tests involves the activity speaking by the learner. Learners are also asked to underline vocabulary that is not understood to be discussed together. Students then listen to the news twice and take notes in each segment. Previously the learner had also been divided into several groups of three or four people to facilitate the discussion of strategies and to make a summary. Based on the prates data, it was concluded that there were three students who got the lowest grades, namely Putri Aditama, Putri Sri Angraini and Resky Hedyla L. Earlier predictions were also made by the teacher based on his teaching experience that students named Putri Aditama were weak in learning Speaking. Thus the focus of the study can be determined, namely on the three students with the lowest grades. Furthermore, from the pre-test results it is also known that. Diana parha gets the highest score. So that later it can be seen whether the metacognitive strategy influences high-ability student.

DISCUSSION

This study aims to determine the effect of the pedagogical cycle on improving speaking to low-ability students. All students involved in the pedagogical cycle are also taught several metacognitive strategies to encourage their understanding in speaking. The research findings show that two students with low speaking ability increased in this study. They felt the metacognitive strategy helped him to better understand the material being tough this is supported by statements from interviews conducted by researchers after the learning process. The main reason students with this less skilled speaking ability show a significant increase is that they have not improved their

knowledge and ability to reconstruct information when listening, before metacognitive learning is carried out. However, systematically and continuously they orchestrate certain cognitive strategies and metacognitive strategies. From the results above, the dominance of development that is not so significant is shown by students with sufficiently skilled listening skills. Three students did not show progress by showing the same results in the pre-test and post-test. This might be because they have mastered a strong understanding and control of several strategies. So their participation in the pedagogical cycle is less significant. From the results of interviews with students who were already proficient and showed only insignificant results, it was found that he used a strategy of maintaining interest in listening. Andi Diana Parha states that by maintaining interest provides a fairly clear in constructing information when she is practicing speaking while namely Putri Aditama, Putri Sri Angraini and Resky Hedyla L they tend to use directed attention strategies, selective attention and visualization in speaking practice .

The implementation of metacognitive strategies in teaching speaking

According to Chamot et al metacognitive strategies consist of four steps. They are planning, monitoring, problem-solving, and evaluating. The four strategies are not always employing sequential but sometimes they are necessary depending on the demands of the task and the interaction between the task and the learner. a. Planning Although the planning strategies happen at the beginning of the learning, sometimes the good learners need to revise it to rethink plans to get back on track .Based on the result of interview and observation of teaching learning process, the students are able to implement the set goal, directed attention in the learning process, but the students could not implement active background knowledge by teacher 1. While based on the results of interviews and observations of the teaching and learning activities in the classroom taught by teacher 2, it was found that in planning strategies, the students were able to implement set goals, directed attention, active background knowledge, and predict. On the set goals indicator, based on the results of observation classroom, the class that taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2 are applied this part. So the students are able to set their own learning goals. This is support with the opinion of Chamot et al that the good learners need to revise the goals of learning to rethink plans to get back on track. On the directed attention indicator, based on the results of observation classroom, the class that taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2 are applied this stage. The importance of directed attention according to Chamot et al that if the learner cannot control the attention to the task, little learning takes place. Direct attention helps the

learner to build up concentration. Next is the indicator of active background knowledge. In classes taught by teacher 1 not applied this stage. This is in line with the opinion of teacher 1 in interview which states that the basic abilities of students in the class are lacking, so it is difficult to relate their background knowledge to the new information that will be received. Whereas the class taught by teacher 2 applies this stage. In the predict indicator, based on the results of observation classroom, class taught by teacher 2 applied this stage. The importance of directed attention according to Chamot et al that anticipating information gives you direction for doing the task because you will be attuned to certain types of information. b. Monitoring Based on the result of interview and observation of teaching-learning process, in the class taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2 the results are obtained at monitoring strategies, the students are able to implement selective attend, deduction/induction, personalize/contextualize, take notes, and cooperate for teacher 1. Whereas based on the results of the interview and observation the activities of the teaching and learning process in the class taught by teacher 2 showed that at monitoring strategies, the 13 students are able to implement selective attend, deduction/induction, personalize/contextualize, take notes, use imagery and cooperate. On the selective attend indicator, based on the results of research on the class taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2, both of them applied this part. The importance of selective attend according to Chamot et al that deciding to focus on specific information make it easier to identify the critical information for learners' goal because they can give full concentration on the important information. In the deduction/induction indicator, based on the results of research in the class, the class that taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2 are applied this part. The importance of deduction/induction according to Chamot et al that think about what you already know helps you get ready for familiarizing yourself with the task. Behaving it, the learner easier understands by linking their background knowledge and new information on the task. On the personalize/contextualize indicator, based on the results of research in the class, the class that taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2 are applied this part. The importance of personalizing according to Chamot et al that Checking language input and output against what you know help the learner ensure that it makes sense. Connecting information to the learners' experience makes the task more meaningful and memorable. In the take notes indicator, based on the results of research in the class, the class taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2 are applied this part. The importance of taking notes according to Chamot et that writing down important information in a form such as a T list, semantic web, or outline can help the learners remember and understand the organization of information. On the use imagery indicator, based on the

result of research in the class, only the class that taught by teacher 2 are applied this part. The importance of use imagery according to Chamot et al that forming picture is a way to check the information makes sense to control the inconsistencies the learner's mental images on the task. In cooperate indicator, based on the results of research in the class, the class taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2 are applied this part. The importance of cooperates according to Chamot et al that working with other people gives the learners better a chance to their ideas or strength so that they can do a better job. c. Problem Solving Based on the result of the interview and observation of the teaching-learning process, the students are able to implement ask the question to clarify and use resources in the class that taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2. The importance of ask the question to clarify according to Chamot et al that asking problems to other people can help the learner solve the problem in comprehending a task. On the use resources indicator, based on the results of research in the class, the class that taught by teacher 1 and teacher 2 are applied this part. The importance of use resources according to Chamot et al that looking up unfamiliar information in a reference source can help the learner solve a complex problem. d. Evaluating 14 Based on the result of the interview and observation of the teaching-learning process in the classroom taught by teacher 1, it was found that in evaluating strategies the students are able to implement evaluate yourself stage. While based on the results of interviews and observations of the teaching and learning activities in the classroom taught by teacher 2, it was found that in evaluating strategies, the students were able to implement summarize stage. In evaluating yourself, based on the results of research in the class, a class that taught by teacher 1 is applied this part. The importance of evaluates yourself according to Chamot that self-evaluating helps the learner identifies the strengths and weakness so that the learner can do better next time. In summarize indicator, based on the results of research in the class, the class taught by teacher 2 is applied this part. The importance of taking summarizes to Chamot et al, that restating the gist the message helps the learner to decide how well he or she understood. Based on the conclusions from the data presented previously, those are from interview data and class observations, it can be concluded that the implementation of metacognitive strategies in the class taught by teacher 2 is more than the implementation of metacognitive strategies in the class taught by the teacher 1. 3. The impact of implementation metacognitive strategies on the students' speaking performance The data obtained based on the results of the teachers' interview and observation classroom. Based on the results interview of the teacher 1 and teacher 2, interviews regarding the impact of metacognitive strategies on the learning process of students from the teacher's view, it

can be concluded that students' abilities and activeness of students in varied classes, where there are active students, there are students who are inactive and there are students in the middle so the implementation of metacognitive strategies is still lacking. However, for students who are able to implement this metacognitive strategy well, the impact on students' learning process is that students will become active and become independent learners and their ability to capture learning outcomes will be much better compared to students who lack implementation in metacognitive strategies. As stated by Corebima & Idrus who suggested that metacognitive strategies are strategies used by students in their learning activities where there are differences between students who are less intelligent and smarter, indicated by differences in metacognitive abilities. If students have metacognition, students will be skilled in using metacognitive strategies. Students who are skilled in using metacognitive strategies will more quickly become independent learners.

CONCLUSION

This small-scale study, specifically conducted in English class as a foreign language that only focuses on simple conversation to less skilled learners, the results show empirical data to support the principle of metacognitive learning using cycles pedagogical can be useful to guide and facilitate students who are less skilled in their speaking skill. The implication of this research is to offer teachers the concept of metacognitive learning in other contexts and practical pedagogical approaches that can be applied to the development of abilities in learning speaking. However, metacognitive learning does not equitably benefit all learners in the class. The teacher must consider how to combine this learning with other learning speaking strategies. Moreover, the development of metacognitive strategies plays a pivotal role in enhancing learners' speaking skills. By fostering awareness, planning, monitoring, and self-evaluation, metacognitive strategies empower students to become more autonomous and reflective speakers. These strategies not only improve fluency and coherence but also boost learners' confidence and motivation in communicative settings. Therefore, integrating metacognitive instruction into speaking lessons is essential for equipping learners with lifelong language learning skills and ensuring more effective and meaningful language use.

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